

lupeol by direct comparison with authentic compound (m. m. p., tlc, ir); α -spinasterol; m. p. 164-166°, acetate m. p. 179-180°, the identity was confirmed through m. m. p., tlc and superimposable ir with an authentic material.

Solanum nigrum L. (Solanaceae) is a commonly occurring herbaceous weed. The tetraploid variety of this species bears orange coloured fruits. Presence of carotenoid in these fruits was reported earlier¹⁴. We have characterised the fruit carotenoid as α -carotene.

Fresh orange coloured berries (50 g) of *S. nigrum* collected locally were ground into a paste with sand and extracted with alcohol at room temperature. The alcoholic extract was shaken with pet. ether several times. The combined pet. ether portions was diluted with ether and to this 30% methanolic KOH was added and kept at room temp in a dark place for 17 hr. The ether layer separated, washed, dried and slowly concentrated. The reddish yellow coloured residue obtained responded to colour reaction for carotenoid. It gave a single spot on thin layer chromatogram. Absorption spectra of material isolated quickly from chromatoplates were recorded in three different solvents, *n*-hexane: 421, 444, 473; CS₂: 475, 510; CHCl₃: 454, 484. It was identified as α -carotene by comparison of the spectral data with that reported for α -carotene¹⁵.

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References

1. H. H. HAINES, "Botany of Bihar and Orissa", 1921, Vol 2, p. 459.
2. S. C. DAS, *Chem. and Ind.*, 1971, 1931.
3. K. MUKHERJEE and L. BOSE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 1112.
4. T. K. CHATTERJEE, A. BASAK, A. K. BARUA, (Mrs.) K. MUKHERJEE and L. N. ROY, *Trans. Bose Res. Inst.*, 1979, 42, 55.
5. W. H. M. W. HERRATH, M. V. S. SULTANBAWA, G. P. WANNIGAM and P. CAVE, *Phytochem.*, 1979, 18, 1835.
6. S. K. NIGAM, G. MISHRA and C. R. MITRA, *Phytochem.*, 1971, 11, 1954.
7. B. E. LEONARD, *Arch. Inst. Pharmacodyn. Ther.*, 1967, 166, 455; *Chem. Abs.*, 1967, 1928d.
8. B. E. LEONARD and H. S. A. SHERRATT, *Arch. Inst. Pharmacodyn. Ther.*, 1967, 166, 424; *Chem. Abs.*, 1967, 1947.
9. B. E. LEONARD and H. S. A. SHERRATT, *Trop. Sci.*, 1967, 9, 122; *Chem. Abs.*, 1968, 67660.
10. P. C. MAITI, *Bull. Bot. Surv. India*, 1963, 5, 269.
11. S. K. NIGAM and C. R. MITRA, *Phytochem.*, 1971, 10, 3313.

12. I. P. VARSHNEY and PRAMOD VYAS, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, 14B, 814.
13. I. P. VARSHNEY, PROMOD VYAS, H. O. SRIVASTAVA and P. P. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1978, 16B, 166.
14. S. L. TANDON and G. R. RAO, *Curr. Sci.*, 1966, 35, 634.
15. K. PRACH and M. V. TRACEY, "Modern Methods of Plant Analysis", 1955, Vol 3, p. 294.

Biologically Active New 1-Substituted-2-mercaptobenzoyl-4-phenylimidazoles

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A number of compounds having various substituents at 1, 2 and 5 positions of imidazole ring have been synthesised and tested for various therapeutic effects¹⁻³. 1-Aryl substitution in imidazole ring^{4,5} enhances the microbial activity. The divalent sulphur containing molecules such as 'NCS' have also been found to possess good antimicrobial properties^{6,7}. Recently, 1-aryl-2-mercaptobenzoyl imidazoles⁸ were found to have good amoebicidal and fungicidal properties.

Considering the above facts, we have synthesised some new 1-substituted-2-mercaptobenzoyl-4-phenylimidazoles and screened them for amoebicidal and fungicidal activity *in vitro*.

Experimental

Synthesis of 1-substituted-2-mercaptobenzoyl-4-phenylimidazole: Equimolecular quantities of 1-substituted-2-mercapto-4-phenylimidazole⁹ and benzoyl chloride and sodium carbonate (0.015 mole) in DMF were refluxed on a steam bath for 2 hr. Later on, the reaction mixture was worked up to get a solid 1-substituted-2-mercaptobenzoyl-4-phenylimidazole. The compounds thus prepared were characterised by elemental analysis and ir spectroscopy. The following characteristic frequencies were obtained for them:

IR KBr: $\nu_{\max}$ (cm⁻¹): 1660 (C=O; C₆H₅-COSR type), 1600 (C=N), 1590, 1490, 1460, 1440 (characteristic for five membered heteroaromatics), 1010-1240 (CH in-plane) and 600, 700 (CH out-of-plane).

Pharmacological screening:

Determination of amoebicidal activity¹⁰ against Schizopyrenus russelli in vitro: The amoebae, *S. russelli*, were grown in monobacterial culture of non-nutrient agar plates (2.5% w/v agar; 0.5% w/v NaCl, pH 6.8-7.0) supplied with a young culture of *Escherichia coli* (2-3 days old grown on nutrient agar slages as food). A dash of fresh *E. coli* was added to freshly harvested amoebae (in 5% saline) to keep

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NOTES

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISTICS AND AMOEBICIDAL ACTIVITY OF 1-SUBSTITUTED-2-MERCAPTOBENZOYL-4-PHENYLIMIDAZOLES

Sl. No.	R	m.p. °C	Yield %	Calcd.		Found		Amoebicidal activity at the minimum inhibitory concentration of	
				%O	%H	%O	%H	1000 µg/ml	500 µg/ml
1.	p-OH ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	101	51	74.5	4.8	75.0	5.7	-	-
2.	α-naphthyl	184	75	76.8	4.5	74.9	4.1	-	+
3.	o-HO ₂ C-C ₆ H ₄	75	57	69.0	4.0	70.0	4.0	-	±
4.	p-HO ₂ C-C ₆ H ₄	66	59	69.0	4.0	70.5	4.2	-	+
5.	p-HO-C ₆ H ₄	110	51	70.9	4.4	70.0	4.3	-	-
6.	o-HO-C ₆ H ₄	44	51	70.9	4.4	70.9	4.1	-	+
7.	m-HO-C ₆ H ₄	174	62	70.9	4.4	70.3	4.5	+	+
8.	o-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	92	61	65.8	3.7	66.0	3.9	+	+

(-)=Negative culture ; (+)=Positive culture ; (±)=Living and dead amoeba.

the amoebae motile and stretched. One drop of this suspension was taken in the cavity of a cavity slide and double the amount of drug concentrate (aqueous solution) to be tested (to compensate for the dilution) was added to it. Slides were incubated in moist chamber at 25 ± 1° and observed for judging the viability of the amoebae (Table 1).

Determination of fungicidal activity¹¹ in vitro : Four species of fungi—*Aspergillus terreus*, *Aspergillus nidulans*, *Candida albicans* and *Cladosporium herbarium* were used in the present study.

Sadbouard's broth (Peptone 10.0 g/litre, dextrose 20.0 g/litre, pH 6.0 approx.) was used as the test medium. The compounds were dissolved in alcohol and 1.0 ml of test solution (100 µg/ml) was added to each tube containing an equal amount of the medium. Tubes were autoclaved at 15 lbs for 15 min prior to inoculation with suitable species of fungus. After inoculation, tubes were incubated at 26 ± 2° for 7 days and vegetative growth recorded visually in each case (Table 2).

TABLE 2—ANTIFUNGAL SCREENING OF 1-SUBSTITUTED-2-MERCAPTOBENZOYL-4-PHENYLIMIDAZOLES

Compound No.	<i>A. terreus</i>	<i>A. nidulans</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>C. herbarum</i>
Control	++++	++++	++++	++++
1.	++	±	+	-
2.	++	+++	+++	++++
3.	-	-	±	+
4.	-	-	+	±
5.	+	+	++	+
6.	++++	++++	+++	+++
7.	-	+	+	-
8.	++	++	+++	-±

++ to +++ = Good growth, positive utilisation and no fungal activity.
 ± to ++ = Slight growth, slight fungicidal activity.
 - = No growth, fungicidal activity.

Results and Discussion

All the synthesised compounds were tested for amoebicidal and fungicidal activities *in vitro*.

Compounds No. 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6 show amoebicidal activity at 1 : 1000 dilution whereas compounds 1 and 5 show good amoebicidal activity at 1 : 500 dilution. Compound No. 3 show slight amoebicidal activity (Table 1).

Compounds No. 3, 4 and 7 show good fungicidal activity. Compounds No. 1, 2 and 8 show slight fungicidal activity (Table 2).

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References

1. P. MELLONI, E. DRADI and W. LONGMANN, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1972, 15, 926.
2. C. CUSAN, R. CRISON, R. N. HOCLOIS and J. J. BOBART, *Ar. forus*, 1966, 16, 28.
3. R. RAFAUR and V. SUNFIR, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1971, 14, 984.
4. P. B. BUDD and H. TOLKONOLY, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1969, 12, 794.
5. P. C. SRIVASTAVA and D. G. STREELA, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1975, 18, 580.
6. M. L. GARG and A. K. MANOV, *Current Science*, 1976, 45, 647.
7. L. DROBNICA, M. Z. PLENJAC and K. AUTOS, *Microbiol.*, 1967, 15, 701.
8. R. C. GUPTA, R. NATH, K. SHANKER, K. P. BHARGAVA and K. KISHORE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 56, 434.
9. AKHTAR ALI and R. K. SAKSENA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, 58, 624.
10. B. N. SINGH, U. SAXENA and S. S. IYER, *Indian J. Expt. Biol.*, 1965, 3, 110.
11. T. N. SRIVASTAVA, S. N. BHATTACHARYA, J. DASGUPTA and S. K. TANDON, *Indian J. Microbiology*, 1968, 8, 65.